

YUSUF KHAS HAJIB'S WORK "KUTADGU BILIG" IS ONE OF THE MOST IMPORTANT EDUCATIONAL ISSUES

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Annotation: *At the main of our ancestral literary heritage is the issue of education. The article is about "Kutadgu Bilig", one of our rare works that can have a positive impact on the younger generation in this regard.*

Key words: *Upbringing, manners, behavior, young generation, harmonious human being, life, nature, intellect, knowledge.*

We know that at the heart of Uzbek classical literature, folklore and all the works created by the great representatives of this literature over the centuries, is the issue of human education, the achievement of human perfection. The heroes of literature and fiction, which are an integral part of it, play an important role model for human education. The student aspires to creative heroes, hating the lives and behaviors of the negative.

It is this hatred that leads him to goodness. There is no need to encourage young people to read more books, to promote reading and teaching,

Literature, by its content and essence, serves to educate people to be good-natured, polite and reasonable. The literature teacher interprets, interprets and summarizes the lives of the protagonists during the Dats. It provides spiritual nourishment to the student.

As a practical aid to literature teachers, class teachers, leaders and librarians of general secondary schools, we present below the book of Yusuf Khas Hajib in order to educate the younger generation, to learn from books, as well as life, to increase their love for reading. We found it necessary to study the effective use of the work "Kutadgu Bilig" and to teach it in a comprehensive way.

"Kutadgu Bilig" (Knowledge that Leads to Happiness and Virtue) was written in 1069. The spiritual need for the work and its artistic value have been highly valued by our ancestors.

The book has been translated into many languages around the world. The poet introduces the book: The word of the wise from beginning to end, is like a necklace. Begins with verses. Since the creation of the book, scholars have praised it as a better

book. The book, which was awarded the title of Khas Hajib in its time and gained great fame, continues to grow in value today. Serves as an important resource in educating young people to become well-rounded people in educational institutions.

In our opinion, it is expedient to divide the work of “Kutadgu bilig” into the following chapters in order to bring it to the attention of young readers and enrich their spiritual world.

Love and respect for nature. Living life with pleasure.

Knowledge and profession are the basis of greatness.

The value of the word, its place in human development.

Appreciate youth, not waste it.

If you want to be healthy, be careful with your tongue.

Live with awareness, vigilance and sensitivity.

The importance of beautiful calligraphy and writing in general.

Serve and learn customs.

About greatness and humility.

The virtues and manners of hospitality.

The advantages of goodness, good intentions and the negative consequences of evil.

Conclusion.

The teacher can also take a creative approach to the above sections, simplifying them according to the students in the classroom. Based on our chapters “Kutadgu bilig” and the statement of the scientist Bakijon Tukliyev, who translated the work into Uzbek, we decided to convey to the minds of students the following: 1. Love and respect for nature. Pleasure in life. Live with passion.

Spring

And the wind of spring came from the east,

The path of beauty opened to the world...

As well as being child of society, man is also a child of nature. Spread in the bosom of nature, the fresh air begins to grow under the clear sky, full of joy.

In the spring, the trees are colorful. The whole universe shines with beauty. Mountains, hills, gardens, and fields are covered in green and white. The world is filled with fragrant scents:

The smell of porcelain,

The whole world is full of perfume...

Students are taught that nature conservation, conservation, keeping the environment clean, not polluting clean drinking water, and not cutting off any leaves of trees are all important tools for human health and longevity.

Cut one, add ten. Concepts of folk pedagogy, such as spitting in water, pouring

salt, cursing the wind, and playing with fire, also strengthen the upbringing of a grooving child. In other words, it encourages students to be environmentally friendly, clean and tidy.

The foundation of knowledge and professional greatness/

There is another wisdom: Hazrat Adam

Knowledge, intellect and reason are revered.

Great knowledge, great learning,

These two great men are full of...

It is well known that human intellect is distinguished from all other living beings by its intelligence. Man solves many puzzles in life with his intellect. Knowledge illuminates the path of human life like a torch. A professional and educated person finds his place in society. The hand benefits the people. He does not suffer materially or spiritually. He value himself and others because of his knowledge. Evil does not enter the street, it does not join the evil. He also has a good name, respect, esteem and glory.

The value of the word,

Its place in human perfection.

Is it better to say too much,

That to say more then hrm...

Sweet words are food for the soul. A kind person is loved and respected by all. It's not okay to say bad things to people like that. One finds respect and prestige not only through hard work, knowledge and profession, but also through language. Words spoken knowingly are wisdom. It's best to keep em short and sweet. Too much talk listening less and listening more is the best quality of a person. Nonsense takes up time and is boring. What a person is immediately known by his words. Is a hypocrite who lies. Wise words lead to action, lead young people to maturity, guide them .

It is advisable for school leaders to teach "Kutadgu bilig" through group discussions, class teachers during spirituality classes, literature teachers in collaboration with librarians through conferences and poetry readings, homework and book teaching. One of the most effective ways to explain the meaning of reading a book. And the teacher fills in and summarizes the content.

Our goal is to learn goodness, spirituality and enlightenment, and most importantly, human behavior and virtues from Yusuf Khas Hajib's book "Kutadgu bilig" at school. From "Kutadgu bilig" it is necessary for humanity and his perfection. You can get as much valuable information as you want.

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